
BASUG LAW JOURNAL

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10493442>

COMPETENCY AND COMPELLABILITY OF WITNESS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF NIGERIAN EVIDENCE ACT AND ISLAMIC LAW

Haruna Alhaji Garba, Babayo Yakubu***

Abstract

This paper is a comparative study of the competency and compellability of witnesses under Islamic law and the Nigerian Evidence Act 2011 (as amended). The law relating to witness is very important in determining the rights and liabilities of individuals in any court or tribunal. It is only through competent witnesses that the aim of the law will be achieved which is the attainment of justice for all. It is important to also know the competent witness in law. The study has adopted the doctrinal method, using comparative approach. The Nigerian law of evidence as govern by the Evidence Act, 2011 (as amended) which the researcher used as primary material in analyzing the requirements for the general competence and compellability of witness and other categories of persons that are protected by the law, though competent but not compellable to give testimony/evidence. However, some other materials were also used like the 1999 Constitution which complements the provision of the Act. While on the part of Islamic law, various requirements of witnesses from the Quran, hadith and Ijma were also discussed in order to give a clear picture of what is required of a witness. Different juristic opinions were considered on the compellability of witness and the duty imposed by Allah on witness when

he is call to testify in the court or anywhere. Thus, the study made recommendations particularly to the law making body to further amend some of the provisions of the Evidence Act by inserting some Islamic law principles on the competence of the witness in order to ensure that guilty person did not escape punishment and an innocent person is set free. This will strengthen the entire judicial system in Nigeria and make it a role model to many countries of the world.

Keywords: Competency, Compellability, Witness, Comparative law

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The basic thing for consideration by the Court when a matter is brought before it for adjudication between the parties is the quality of the witnesses of the litigants and the Court will give judgment in favour of the person with competent witness not the person with more number of witnesses, therefore the Court will look at the quality not the quantity of the witnesses to arrive at a just decision.

This paper will examine the issues related to the competence as well as compellability of witnesses under the Nigerian law as contained in the Evidence Act and Islamic law as contained in the sources of Sharia such as the Quran, Hadith, Ijma and Ijtihad of Islamic scholars. However, for the purpose of convenience, the paper will be divided into two parts. The first part will examine the categories of people that are regarded as competent and non-compellable witnesses under the Act and the second part will do the same thing but under Islamic law.

2.0 COMPETENT WITNESSES UNDER THE EVIDENCE ACT 2011

A competent witness is a person who is regarded by law to be fit and proper to give evidence.¹ Competence in this context is a general competence which is distinct from competence to give specific evidence as in the case of expert witness. The latter mainly depends on special skills while the former usually depend on possession of unimpaired intellect. Section 175 of the Evidence Act 2011 gives a general requirement for the competence of a witness to testify before the court of law or tribunal. Subject to a few exceptions, all persons are competent to give evidence. The main reason of incompetency of a witness is a defective intellect, which will prevent him or her from making rational statements. Such deficiency may be as a result of immaturity, insanity or mental disorder or extreme old age. The section provides:

“All person shall be competent to testify, unless the court considers that they are prevented from understanding the questions put to them, or from giving

* LLB. BL. LLM. Faculty of law, Department of Islamic law, Bauchi State University, Gadau. agharunakm@gmail.com. 08037405179

** LLB. BL. LLM. Faculty of law, Department of Islamic law, Bauchi State University, Gadau. yakubumisau1031@gmail.com. 08039647387

¹ Fedilis Nwadialo, *Modern Nigerian law of Evidence*. (Unilag Press, 1999,) 454.

rational answers to those questions, by reason of tender years, extreme old age, diseases, whether of body or mind, or any other cause of the same kind”.

It is clear from the above provision that the only thing that will bar a person from being considered a competent witness is not age or unsoundness of mind, but his ability to give rational answers to the questions put to him. Therefore, the study will examine and analyze the extent of the competence of the persons mentioned in Section 175.

2.1 CHILD

Basically, there are two conditions that determine the competence of a child to give testimony. First, he or she must not be prevented from understanding the questions asked or from giving rational answers to those questions by the reason of age. This condition, as provided by the cited section above, regulates the reception of the testimony of a child. The second is that, child oral evidence shall be giving on oaths or affirmations. This is based on the general principle of the law of evidence that, every oral evidence must be on oath or affirmation.² However, a proviso is provided in Section 209 of the Evidence Act 2011, which serves as an exception to the requirement of oath or affirmation thus, allowing the admissibility of the unsown testimony of a child. It is stated as follows:

“In any proceeding in which a child who has not attained the age of 14 is tendered as a witness, such child shall not be sworn and shall give evidence otherwise than on oath or affirmation, if in the opinion of the court, he is possessed of sufficient intelligence to justify the reception of his evidence and understands the duty of speaking the truth”.

Therefore, it is clear from the above citation that the condition of an oath or affirmation before a testimony will be accepted has exempted a child i.e. a child must not satisfy that requirement. But, the question may be asked as who is to be considered as a child. The Act has defined a child to mean a person who has not attained the age or under the age of 14 years.³ So, it is clear that, from 14 years old and above a person is not considered a child for the purpose of giving evidence. Therefore, he or she is competent to be sworn and give evidence. But, with regard to child who is 13 years old and below, his testimony may be

² Section 205 of the Evidence Act.

³ Section 209 (2) Evidence Act

admitted subject to conditions mentioned above even though the law requires corroboration by the judge before conviction.⁴ In case the only material evidence of the prosecution is the unsworn testimony of a child that implicates the dependent or accused.

2.2 OLD PERSONS AND PERSONS SUFFERING FROM DISEASE OF THE BODY, MIND OR OTHER AFFLICTIONS

An old person, no matter how old he is, is a competent witness. Similar to the case of a child of tender years, once he can be able to understand the questions and can give rational answers to those questions he is deemed competent.⁵ It appears that there is no such case in Nigeria within the limited knowledge of the writer at the point in time. It is therefore, submitted with some level of confidence that the same method of test used in the case of a child would be used in case of a person of old age.

Similarly, a person suffering from disease, whether of body or mind, is a competent witness unless the court considers that he is prevented from understanding the questions asked him or from giving rational answers to those questions based on the said diseases. This provision covers any person who is unable to understand questions and give rational answers to the questions by reason of any other cause of the same kind. Also, a person does not become incompetent merely because he is drunk, he must be drunk to the extent that he cannot understand the questions put to him and he cannot give answers that are rational. Therefore, a person of unsound mind, even if certified, is not ipso facto incompetent to give evidence.⁶

2.3 DUMB PERSONS

A dumb person is considered by the Act to be a competent witness. He may give his testimony in another manner, in which he makes it intelligible as by writing or signs. It is required that the writing and signs must be made in an open court and the evidence given/presented shall be deemed as oral evidence.⁷

Therefore, from the above discussion it is very clear that under the Nigerian law of evidence, every individual is a competent witness irrespective of age, status, color, sex or

⁴ Ibid, (3).

⁵ Section 175 Evidence Act.

⁶ T.Akinola Aguda, *The law of Evidence*, 3rd edition, (Spectrum Book Limited, 1999) 305.

⁷ Section 176(1) and (2) Evidence Act.

race, unless he or she does not pass the test of Section 175 of the Act i.e., from understanding the question put to him and his inability to give rational answers, before he will be declared incompetent by the court. However, reason of existence of any family relationship or the witness may likely benefit from the outcome of the proceedings or he is of certain belief does not disqualify a person from been competent to testify.⁸

Under the Nigerian Evidence Act, 14 years is provided as the minimum age limit of a competent witness. This provision has led to rest the unnecessary argument made by the lawyers in the Repeal Act, which does not specify the age limit for a child to give testimony. Thus, due to the amendment of the Nigerian Evidence Act in 2011 by the National Assembly, there are no much judicial authorities on the issue of witnesses because most of the controversial provisions were amended such as the argument as to age limit and whether the child understands the duty of telling the truth, which were all repealed by the new act. This is why the research does not include Nigerian cases on the competency of witnesses, which are somehow obsolete, until when the new amended provisions are tested in the court.

3.0 NON-COMPELLABLE WITNESSES

The general rule is that every competent witness can be compelled to give evidence unless he can prove otherwise that he is exempted by any law to testify. A compellable witness is a person who can be lawfully compelled by the court to testify. Unlike competent witnesses who may choose whether to testify or not, a compellable witness has no option on whether to attend court when summoned. In fact he will be cited for court contempt if he fails to appear and testify before the court or tribunal.⁹

However, certain categories of people are exempted from being compellable either by the Act or other legislations like the Constitution, which accords privileges to some office holders during their tenure in office. Thus, it is said that every compellable witness is a competent witness but not every competent witness is compellable. Therefore, we will examine non-compellable witnesses as provided by different Nigerian laws.

⁸ Ibid, 178- 180

⁹ Taiwo osipatan, 340.

3.1 SPOUSES

The spouse of an accused person is not a compellable witness for the prosecution unless the other spouse who is on trial applies that his spouse should give evidence against him. However, the non-compellability of a spouse as a witness is a general rule but there are exceptions. In some offences, if committed by either of the spouses they will be deemed as compellable and competent witness to each other. Some of the offences includes: Indecent practice between males, defilement of girls under 13 years old, child abduction, bigamy, procuration and slave dealings. In fact, the non-compellability of a spouse is not absolute, which means certain exceptional circumstances are provided by the Act, Section 182 (2) provides that when any of the spouse is charged with an offence other than the one mentioned in sub section 1 of this section, they shall only be a competent and compellable witness upon the application of the person charged i.e. the consent of either of the spouse must be sorted and obtained before he can testify. Also subsection (3) goes on to say:

Nothing in this Section shall make a husband compellable to disclose any communication made to him by his wife during the marriage or a wife compellable to disclose any communication made to her by her husband during the marriage

A similar provision is made in Section 187 of the Act, even though with an addition that either of the spouse shall not be permitted to testify which suggests that even if it is voluntary; except with the consent of the spouse, this is applicable whether in a criminal or civil action.

The wife of an accused person is not a compellable witness against the person charged jointly with her husband even though competent and if her evidence would incriminate her husband, then she can only give evidence on her husband's application.¹⁰

3.2 ACCUSED PERSON

The accused person's competency and compellability are regulated by the combined effect of sections 179 and 180 respectively. This is so whether he is called as witness or charged as an accused person. An accused person is exempted from being compelled to be a

¹⁰ Afe Babalola, *Law & practice of Evidence in Nigeria* (University press, 2009) 407.

witness either for himself or for the prosecution. This is contained under Section 36 (11) of the Nigeria 1999 Constitution. It provides; "No person who is tried for a criminal offence shall be compelled to give evidence at his trial". Under the Act, particularly in paragraph (a) of Section 180, made a proviso which prevents the court from compelling the accused to testify except by his own application. It provides that "a person so charge shall not be called as a witness in pursuance of this section except upon his own application". Paragraph (g) also provides a privilege to the witness not to answer certain questions that may tend to show that he has committed or has been convicted of or been charged with any offence other than that which he is then charge, or he is of bad character, unless it can show that by establishing that fact in previous proceedings, will be a proof on the current charge or either by himself or legal practitioner as questions with a view of establishing his good character or he is giving evidence against any other person charged with the same offence. He is deemed to have waived his right not to be compelled to answer question in the trials. Moreover, Section 183 generally protects a witness in criminal trials not to be compelled to incriminate himself by answering questions which, in the opinion of the court, have a tendency to expose him to any criminal charges or to any penalty or forfeiture which the judge considers as reasonable. The above section seems to deal only with the witness in the criminal trials, but the Act provides alternative section to cover civil trials particularly with regard to documents, section 184 provided that no person who is not a party to a suit shall be compelled to produce his title deeds to any property or any document by virtue of which he holds any property as pledge or mortgage except what he has agreed in writing to produce them. Therefore, the Act protects a person who is not party but in possession of a document not to be compelled to produce such document.

Section 177 also exempts banker or an officer of the bank or other financial institutions from being compelled to produce financial books in any legal proceeding in which a bank or other financial institutions is not made a party. So, it can be said that the protection of the law against being compelled does not stop on a person alone but it is extended to companies which are regarded by law to be a juristic person, capable of being sued and be sued in its cooperate name.

3.3 JUDGES/PUBLIC OFFICERS

The judges, justices or kadis are not compellable witness as to their conduct in a proceeding whom they presided over as judges.¹¹ Even though he may be examined as to other matters which occurred in his presence while he was so acting. This protection is not absolute because it is only applicable on matters that happened in court but they are deemed competent and compellable in other matters.

The provision of Section 189 protects the police officers or any public officer authorized by any written law to investigate or prosecute an offence from been compelled to disclose the source of any information to the commission of an offence which he is so authorized to investigate and prosecute. Additionally, no public revenue officer shall be compelled to disclose the source of any information as to the commission of any offence against the public revenue. Consequently, section 191 provides that no public officer shall be compelled to disclose communication made to him in official confidence, when he considers that the public interest will suffer by the disclosure. However, a proviso is provided to section 191 to the effect that the public officer shall, on the order of the court, disclose to the judge alone in his chambers the substance of communication in question. If the judge is satisfied, the communication shall be done in private in accordance with Section 36 (4) of the 1999 Constitution as amended.

3.4 COMMUNICATION BETWEEN CLIENT AND LEGAL PRACTITIONER

Professional relationships which involves communication between clients and their lawyers is regarded by law to be a privilege. Section 192 provides that no legal practitioner shall, at any time, be permitted, unless with his client express consent, to disclose any communication made to him in the course of the trials and for the purpose of his employment as a legal practitioner by or on behalf of his client, or to state the contents or conditions of any document with which he has become acquainted with in due course and for the purpose of his professional employment or to disclose any advice given by him to his client, provided that the communication shall not be made for the purpose of any illegal

¹¹ Section 188 Evidence Act.

act or commission of any crimes or fraud. This rule also includes clerks and interpreters in the office of the legal practitioner.¹²

3.5 PRESIDENT/VICE PRESIDENT OR GOVERNOR/DEPUTY GOVERNOR

The President and his Deputy or State Governors and their Deputies are generally competent witnesses by the provision of Section 175 of the Act discussed above. But they are not compellable witnesses as long as they are holding that offices. Their immunity is provided by the constitution of Nigeria as follows: “no process of any court requiring or compelling the appearance of such a person holding the office of President or vice President, Governor or Deputy Governor shall be applied or issue”.¹³

The Constitution confers the holders of the offices mentioned above immunity from criminal and civil actions against their persons while occupying the office. However, the non-compellability of those office holders is limited to their tenure in office. Once they vacate the office, they become compellable witnesses even if the causes of action happened before, during or after their tenure in office. The protection is for the holders of the office and not the office itself because the Constitution allows such holders of the office to be sued in their official capacities.¹⁴ The law allows such office holders to only testify when in office, if he voluntary decides to relinquish his right i.e. immunity.

3.6 DIPLOMATIC AGENTS

Foreign sovereigns, their ambassadors and other diplomatic agents are not compellable witnesses even though they are competent witness. They can only testify if they waive their immunity. Section 1 of the Diplomatic Immunities and Privileges Act 1962 provides that “Foreign envoys and every consular officer, the members of families of those persons, the members of their official or domestic staff and the members of the families of their official staff, shall be accorded immunity from suit and legal process”. But by virtue of Section 2 of the same Act, all the persons mentioned above can waive their immunity if they so wish. Section 3 and 4 of the same Act provides a similar rule in respect to the High Commissioners from commonwealth countries, their officials and their families, while

¹² Section 193 &195 Evidence Act.

¹³ Section 308 (1) (a), (b) & (c) and 308 (3) Constitution of Nigeria 1999

¹⁴ Ibid, 308 (3).

Sections 11 and 15 also make similar provisions with respect to representatives of certain recognized international organizations.¹⁵

Subject to the above provisions, all foreigners are competent and compellable witnesses in Nigeria even if they cannot understand the language of the court which is English. An interpreter will be provided for them if they cannot speak English.

4.0 COMPETENT WITNESSES UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

A competence witness under Islamic law is a person who is validly allowed or permitted by the Sharia to give testimony in any proceeding before the court. Islamic jurists have divided the conditions of the witness to two categories i.e. with regard to the admissibility and capability to give testimony. For the purpose of this research, we are more concerned with the conditions that make a witness competent in the eyes of the Sharia in order to give testimony. Unlike the provisions of the Evidence Act, which are only concerned with the mental faculty of person, Islamic law provides stringent conditions which must be satisfied by the witness in order to be deemed competent. This condition goes beyond one's mental capacity as they also include spiritual, physical as well as mental competence.

We will now examine the various requirements for a witness (shahid) before he will be considered competent under Islamic law: -

i. Islam: Muslim jurists are of the opinion that being a Muslim is one of the conditions of being a witness.¹⁶ Their opinion is based on the verse of the Holy Quran where Allah says: "And call two witnesses from among your men; and if two men be not available then a man and two women, of such you approve as witnesses".¹⁷ In another verse Allah says: "and call to witness two just persons from among you; and bear true witness for Allah".¹⁸ It can be clearly understood from the above verses that non-Muslims are not recognized as competent witnesses under Islamic law. However, Islamic jurists are divided as to the exceptional circumstances where the testimony of a non-Muslim may be accepted.

¹⁵ Aguda, 301.

¹⁶ Ibn Rushud Muhammad bin Al-qurtubi, *Bidayah Al-Mujtahid wa Nihaya Al-Muqtasid* (Maktaba Al-kuliyah Al-Azhar, Egypt, 1964) 499.

¹⁷ Quran2 verse 283.

¹⁸ Quran65 verse 2.

One of the circumstances in which a testimony of a non-Muslim may be accepted is in the case of a bequest by a Muslim on a journey, where there are no Muslims but only a non-Muslim is available. This is the view of Imam Abu Hanifa, Ibrahim al-Nakai and Imam Awza'i. Even at that, they hold that, there should be no any Muslim that can testify but where there is a Muslim who can testify, then it is not permissible for a non-Muslim to testify i.e. he is not competent. They rely on the following verse of the Holy Qur'an:

"O ye who believe! The right evidence among you, when death comes to one of you, at the time of making a will, is of two just men from among you; or two others not from among you, in case you be journeying in the land and the calamity of death befalls you".¹⁹

Imam Shafi'i and Maliki on the other hand do not allow the testimony of a non-Muslim even in cases where the witness is a non-Muslim who accompanies a Muslim during the course of a journey. Their argument is based on the qualities of a witness provided in the Quran: "And get two witness among you". Therefore, a competent witness must be a Muslim who is just, and a non-Muslim is not among those who are just and not among the accepted community, because they are people who deny the authority of Allah. They also argue that, it is not mentioned in the above cited verse that a non-Muslim can give testimony as to the will of a Muslim on journey. They are of the view that, the word "minkum" in the verse means "your family" and does not mean "those who are your co-religionist" and also hold that the verse was abrogated.²⁰

Evidence of a non-Muslim against a Muslim in times of emergency; the general rule is that; non-Muslims are not competent witnesses against a Muslim. However, Muslim scholars like Ibn Abbas, Ibn Taimiyah and Ibn Qayyim allowed the testimony of a non-Muslim against a Muslim in the case of necessity. They based their argument by analogy that, since Allah allows testimony of a non-Muslim against the Muslim in case of bequest, it means that in cases of necessity the testimony of a non-Muslim can be accepted. Moreover, going by the present reality, the opinion of the Muslim jurists who reject the testimony of a non-

¹⁹ Quran5 verse 106.

²⁰ Saedon, Mahmud Saedon a. Othman, An Introduction to Islamic Law of Evidence, translated from Bahasa Malaysia by Raden Ahmad Shauki R. Hisam, Kuala Lumpur, Hizbi sdn. Bhd, 1999. 54.

Muslim will not contribute to the course of justice, because the sole aim of justice is to award equitable remedy to the wronged. It could be possible in the past, the rate of interaction between Muslim and non-Muslim may not be as frequent as it is obtained today. It will be an unfortunate fate to a murder victim whose murder took place in the full view of a non-Muslim; the non-Muslim witness who is deemed not competent to testify²¹.

The opinion of experts who are not Muslims may be accepted, according to Imam Malik. A judge may accept the medical opinion of a doctor who is not a Muslim. Even though some jurists hold that, this cannot amount to testimony, it can be considered as a knowledge which a judge acquires from an expert. Such an opinion can be accepted even if it is mooted by one doctor.²²

In the context of the testimony of a non-Muslim against themselves is admissible i.e. they are competent to testify for or against each other. This is the view of Imam Hanbali and Hanafi. Imam Hanbali allowed the testimony of zimmi against a musta'man as a zimmi's status is higher than that of musta'man. A zimmi is closer in status to a Muslim. Abu Hanafi rejected the testimony of musta'man against a zimmi, but the evidence of musta'aman against themselves is allowed.

ii. Probity (Adil) is one of the legal requirements of a witness, Allah says that "...call to witness two men of probity from among you" The verse has invariable challenged the validity of the evidence of impious persons. Therefore, before a witness is considered competent he must be a just person. The Prophet (SAW) was equally reported to have said "The testimony of a dishonest or of an adulterer or adulteress is not acceptable" The testimony of an impious person, a notorious liar or a person of void temperament is not acceptable. Whoever possesses these qualities lacks probity. The Hanafi School is of the opinion that what is required of probity in property cases is the simple declaration of Islam, that the person should not be found guilty of what is capable of tarnishing his image and has allowed the testimony of two impious people on marriage. Maliki jurists have allowed the testimony of impious people and the testimony of a people of unknown behaviour in the case of necessity.

²¹ Ibid.

²² M.T. El-Imairi, *Evidence and Court Procedure In Islam* (A.B.U Press, 1990) 41.

Islamic jurists have given different definitions of Adil i.e. who is an Adil. Imam Abu Hanifah is of the view that justness that is required should be reasonable as to be fit to an ordinary Muslim and there is no blameworthy attributes on the person of the witness.²³ According to Shafi'i "a just person is someone who stays away from major sins, and has no tendency to commit minor sins, possessing true faith and of calm disposition even in a state of anger and able to protect his honor."²⁴ While Hanbali sees, just person as someone who adheres to the dictates of religion and the truth of his speech and conduct.²⁵ According to Maliki, being just means protecting one's religion by staying away from major sins, being vigilant with regards to minor sins, fulfilling trusts and having good social interaction. Jurists here do not mean people who have never committed any sin because it will be too harsh a condition because no one will qualify if it is made a prerequisite condition.

The jurists are unanimous on the issue that the testimony of an impious person is not accepted unless he repents and mends his ways. But, they are not unanimous on the nature of offence that leads to impiety. According to Imam Maliki, Shafi'i and Hanbali, once an impious person repents for his sins, his testimony will be accepted irrespective of the nature of the offence; whether it is murder, adultery or defamation. Imam Abu Hanifah too accepted the offence of defamation. Their source of difference is the verse were Allah says:

"And thus who launch (a false) charge against chaste women, and produce not four witnesses flog them with eighty stripes and reject their evidence ever after, for such men are wicked transgressors, unless they repent there after and mend their conduct, for Allah is oft-forgiving most merciful".²⁶

According to the three schools, the last proviso of repentance has validated the acceptance of the testimony of an impious person. Abu Hanifah still maintains that the proviso only validates the acceptance of such evidence of an impious person for offences other than defamation (Qazaf).²⁷

²³ Saedon, 57.

²⁴ Ibid,

²⁵ ibid

²⁶ Quran 24 verse 4.

²⁷ M.S. Abubakar, *Some Principles of Islamic law of Evidence-Murafa'at* (AMD design & Communication, 2012) 47.

iii. Soundness of mind (Aqal): A person of unsound mind is not a competent witness in Islam. His testimony is not admissible because of his mental position. The Prophet is reported to have said “three persons are exonerated from responsibility: An insane until he recovers, a minor until he attains puberty and a sleeping person until he wakes up”. Based on the above tradition, an insane person is exempted from giving testimony because he is deprived by reason of his state of mind from giving and comprehending the nature of evidence he is expected to give. As such, he cannot give satisfactory evidence which the court can base its judgment. “O ye who believe do not attempt to pray when you are in state of drunkenness until you know what you are saying...”²⁸ The witness must be mentally sound, he must be in possession of his mental faculties both when he conceives the incident and when he is to testify. People notorious for bad memory or lethargy are not competent witnesses.²⁹

iv. Adulthood (Balig): The Islamic jurists unanimously agree that, the witness must be an adult and not a minor. This is based on the Hadith of the Prophet (SAW), where he says “three persons are exonerated from responsibility: An insane until he recovers, a minor until he attains puberty...” However, in some circumstances, some jurists like Imam Malik have allowed the evidence of a minor in case of injuries, provided the child is a *mumayyiz* (age of discernment). It is a fact that during such outings, children are not accompanied by adults. If their testimony is not accepted despite a strong presumption, then justice will have been perverted.

Islamic jurists have laid down conditions that must be satisfied before the testimony of a child could be accepted in injury cases:

- 1- That the children have not returned to their homes (this is to safeguard against any intervention from an adult)
- 2- The children should unanimously give the same testimony e.g. when asked who injured Abdullahi, they unanimously say it is Musa.
- 3- They should be separated at the time of giving evidence.

²⁸ Quran 4 verse 43.

²⁹ Anwarullah, *Principal of Evidence in Islam* (Malaysia, As-Noordeen, 2010)5.

4- The minors' status should be of a free person and there should be more than one such minor witness.

5- Their testimony will be admitted if there is no adult at the scene of the crime.

6- Their testimony will never be admitted for or against the adult. The injury must be between minors.

v. Capacity of expression and sight (al-kalam wal Ru'ya): A competent witness in Islam must be able to express himself. The testimony of a dumb person who cannot express himself is not acceptable, even if he can write his evidence. This is the opinion of the Hanafi School but according to the Maliki School, the testimony of a dumb person is acceptable provided that his gestures could be understandable. Therefore, the divorce of a dumb and deaf persons whether in writing or by gesture, is acceptable as well as his marriage and sales.

Islamic jurists unanimously agreed that the witness must not be blind i.e. he must be capable of seeing. The Hanafi School has outrightly rejected the evidence of a blind person, but the Maliki and Hanbali schools have allowed his testimony on issues that are pertaining to hearing and he understood the voice, his testimony is admissible and valid in cases of marriage, divorce, sale, lease, paternity, endowment and general possession. On accepting the evidence of a blind man, Imam Malik relied on the fact that some companions, when they came to the Prophets family, they used to enquire from them about religious matters from behind the curtain without seeing them. By analogy, such legal verdicts are equated with oral evidence which was rendered without seeing the person rendering it. Thus, is applied to blind person. But the evidence of blind person is rejected by Imam Malik, Shafi'i and Hanbali in hudud cases such as zina, murder, and armed robbery.³⁰

vi. Good memory (al-hifz wal Dabt): A competent witness is required to have strong memory so as to enable him to relate accurately in his testimony about a particular event that he had witnessed. The truth of his testimony depends on the strength of his memory of important facts which is related to a particular issue. The testimony of a person possessing poor memory. Forgetfulness, in firmness of speech, inaccuracy or something that is

³⁰ Ibid, 50.

related, is not admissible. It is therefore, clear that this condition is designed to guarantee the quality of witnesses to make sure the court has arrived at a just decision.

vii. Freedom (Hurriyyah): According to Hanafi, Maliki and Shafi'i, a slave is not a competent witness in Islam, because only a free person can testify. This is the view of the majority of Muslim scholars. They rely on the following verse where Allah says "Allah set forth for you the parable of a slave who is owned, having no power over anything; and a free man whom we have provided with a fair provision from us and he spends thereof secretly and openly..."³¹

The Zahiri School on the other hand, accepted the testimony of a slave witness. They based their argument that the most important factor is that the witness is adil. As such, slavery is not a restriction against giving evidence, unless it had been categorically prohibited by the Quran, Sunnah or Ijma.

The above conditions for the competence of witness as (Shahid) are general conditions which must be satisfied by every witness before his evidence is allowed to be presented in court. This is based on the Quran, Hadith and Ijma of Muslim Jurists. This is because the aim of the sharia is that justice should be done to everybody including the plaintiff, dependent, witness as well as the society in general. So, in a nut shell, anybody who satisfies the above conditions is considered to be a competent witness in Islamic law i.e. he is fit and proper to give testimony.

However, there are some conditions which are specific to the person giving evidence, which will make him incompetent due to either his affiliation to the parties or he has a special interest in the matter. Therefore, we are going to consider such circumstances.

A testimony between two persons who are affectionate to one another or enemies is prohibited. It is suspected that the affection between them could prevent speaking the truth. It is also suspected that, enmity could lead to perjury. Some jurists are of the view that, son cannot testify in favour of his father and vice-versa. Neither a mother nor her son (or daughter) can testify in favour of one another but they are allowed to testify against one another.

³¹ Quran 16 verse 75.

Enemies on worldly affairs cannot testify against one another but if the enmity is based on religious grounds, such a testimony can be accepted, because suspicion may not be there in view of the fact Islam prohibits perjury.

A servant cannot be a competent witness for his master because there is probability that he cannot tell anything against the interest of his master.³² This is the opinion of Imam Malik, Imam Abu Hanifah and Imam Ahmad relying on the following authority. Aisha (may Allah be pleased with her) reported that the messenger of Allah (SAW) said that “the testimony of a dishonest malevolent is not accepted against his brother Muslim nor the testimony of a son in favor of his father and vice-versa” It is also reported from the prophet (SAW) said that “The testimony of a dishonest male and female and that of the rancorous shall not be admitted against their brothers nor that of a person in favor of another person who maintains him.” In another narration, it is said that “The testimony of disputants shall not be accepted.” The testimony of a spouse in favour of one another is also not acceptable for similar reasons.³³

However, the testimony of close relations or associates apart from those mentioned above in favour of another is permissible.³⁴ On the other hand, Caliph Umar Ibn Khattab, Shurayh, Umar Ibn Abdul Aziz, Ibn Munzir and Imam Shafi'i hold that the testimony of a son in favour of his father and vice-versa is acceptable provided they are trusted and competent witnesses i.e. satisfied the general requirement of a witness discussed above.

The evidence of a co-owners in the interest of some ownership or partnership should not be accepted i.e. they are not competence witnesses against each other.³⁵ This may not be unconnected with the likely hood of telling lies.

5.0 COMPELLABILITY OF WITNESSES UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

The general rule is that Islamic law has imposed a duty on every Muslim as an individual to give evidence or testimony on issues that he has knowledge on, whenever a request is made of him to do so. As failure of the witnesses to give testimony will cause the

³² El-Imari, 51.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Sayyed Sabiq, *Fiqh Sunnah* (Darul-Fikr, Beirut, vol.2, 260)

³⁵ El-Emari, 54.

miscarriage of justice. This can be clearly understood from the provision of the Quran and Sunnah. Allah says:

*“O ye who believe! Stand out firmly for justice, as witnesses to Allah even against yourselves or your parents or your kin and whether it be (against) rich or poor. For Allah can best protect both. Follow not the lust (of your hearts) lest ye swerve, and if ye distort (justice) or decline to do justice, verily Allah is well-acquainted with all that ye do”.*³⁶

Muslim are enjoined to give testimony even if it will be against their personal interest, because doing that will confer to the Muslim of being just which is a good quality expected of every believer. Allah says that “... Conceal not evidence, for whom ever conceal it his is tainted with sin and Allah know best all that ye do”³⁷. From the above verse, it can be understood that concealing evidence is a sin. Allah also says that “witness should not refuse (giving evidence) when they are called on...”³⁸

The scholars have divided the compellability of witnesses into two categories: Compellability in Hudud cases and non Hudud cases:

- a. Non Hudd offences; Islamic jurists are unanimous that in giving testimony in non hudud cases it is obligatory on the Muslim community i.e. fard kifayah, i. e. if some members of the community have volunteered to give evidence, it means that the other members of the community are exempted from responsibility or liability but it will be Fard ayn if there is only one person in the community.³⁹

According to the majority of Islamic jurists, it is not obligatory on a person to give testimony in Hudud cases when he is giving option to testify or not. Ibn Al-Human of the Hanafi School holds that witnesses have the option to either reveal or conceal the evidence, but he opines that is better for him to conceal (afdal). al-Sharazi of the Shafi'i School also holds that, it is not recommended for a witness to give evidence in hudud offences. This means that it is better to hide such evidence, but if the witness chooses to give testimony, then he should be considered as competent witness and his testimony should be accepted. The authority

³⁶ Quran 4 verse 135.

³⁷ Quran 2 verse 283.

³⁸ Quran 2 verse 282.

³⁹ Saedon, 12.

for the above opinion is the hadith of the Prophet (SAW) reported by Abu-Huraira that “Reject hudud offences as long as you can reject it with one rejection”⁴⁰. In another narration, the Prophet (SAW) says “Those who covers the fault of a Muslim, Allah will cover his fault on earth and in the hereafter.”

In view of the above opinion, critics may think that, this will encourage people to commit more crimes as it is not obligatory for a witness to give testimony. As such, this will defeat the main spirit of the Sharia and may amount to the miscarriage of justice. According to Ibn Abi-Dam⁴¹ “when the testimony of a person is required by a judge (or court) thereafter such testimony or evidence and the adducing there of becomes an amanah (trust) and also fard ayn. This view is in line with the spirit of the above mentioned verses on the duty of Muslims to give evidence with truth even if it will be against himself or his father or any of his family members for failure of the person to give evidence will be sinful in the side of Allah.⁴²

Consequent upon the above, some jurisdictions (countries) provides for a fee to be given to the witness for him to cover his transport expenses. Failure to give such fees, even if subpoena by the court, the witness will not be liable for contempt. In Nigeria there is no such provision with regard to paying a witness when summoned to court to give evidence. The reason for that is, there is no any codified Islamic law of procedure that governs the court proceedings. Reliance is only giving to the early books writing by the jurist (fuqahau) of Maliki School (mazhab).

It is therefore recommended that, the rules of procedures in our courts should be amended to cover such realities of life. It will at least encourage the witnesses’ easy ways of telling the truth in our courts as believers are enjoined to speak the truth even if it is against themselves or their love ones.

6. CONCLUSION

The ultimate goal of every judicial system is the attainment of justice. This is true in Islamic law, Nigerian law, Common law and Civil law. Even though the methods followed by these

⁴⁰ Ibid, 13.

⁴¹ Ibid, 14.

⁴² Ibid.

systems to attain justice may differ. The imperative of justice to human existence is unquantifiable. Only justice can bring the society together without which there will be chaos. The court is considered to be the best institution where aggrieved individuals can take their case to for redress against any wrong done to them with the expectation of remedies. The court, on its part cannot just grant the claims of the claimant without asking the claimant to bring proof(s). Usually it is through the testimony of the competent witnesses that the claim can be established, based on the standard required by Law depending on the nature of the case i.e. whether criminal or civil.